

ANALYSING THE FINANCIAL VIABILITY OF THE 50MW BANGWEULU SOLAR PLANT IN ZAMBIA USING FINPLAN

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Executive Summary

The financial viability of the Bangweulu 50 MW Power Plant using FINPLAN was analysed by exploring three scenarios to assess the impact on shareholder dividends in a solar power plant project. The first scenario involved varying electricity prices, indicating that the base price of ZMW 1.5 per KWh resulted in the highest dividends and the shortest waiting period for shareholders to access their dividends. The second scenario focused on increasing the quantity of electricity produced, revealing that all tested productivity increases led to higher shareholding dividends without resulting in a lag time before dividend payments. However, increasing productivity to 75% above the base level resulted in higher dividends and ensured better efficiency. The third scenario examined varying loan repayment periods, demonstrating that shorter repayment periods were more profitable in the short term, while longer periods reduced plant profitability. The findings provide insights into the factors influencing the financial performance of solar power plant projects and offer practical implications for project planning and decision-making. It was recommended that exploring price reduction, increasing production and focussing on loans with shorter repayment periods would improve the financial viability and profitability of the solar power plant.

1. Introduction

Zambia's current electricity generation capacity is 2,800 MW, with 83% coming from hydro-based renewable energy (NEP 2019) (Figure 1). However, national electricity access stands at an average of 31%, with only 79.7% of the urban population and 8.4% of the rural population having access to power (NEP 2019). The Government of the Republic of Zambia aims to achieve universal electricity access for all citizens by 2030. Recognizing the

importance of energy for economic development, the government is committed to developing and maintaining energy infrastructure and services (MoE 2022). Zambia has been transitioning to a "green economy" to balance economic growth with environmental quality and social inclusion (Moonga and Chileshe 2019). Despite historical reliance on hydropower, efforts to diversify the energy mix have been limited, with renewable energy sources (excluding hydro) accounting for less than 1% of the energy mix in 2018 (ERB 2020). Climate change has impacted hydropower generation, leading to a power deficit of up to 810 MW in 2020 (IRP 2020). To address this, the Zambian Government is committed to implementing a renewable energy investment plan, including the development of the Bangweulu Solar Plant, to improve the energy mix.

Figure 1. Zambia's electric energy profile for the year 2022 (Source: MoE 2022)

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The study will evaluate the financial performance of the 50MW Bangweulu Solar Plant in Zambia using factors such as investment costs, operational expenses, revenue generation, projected cash flows, and return on investment.

1.2 Objective and aims

To analyse the financial viability of the Bangweulu 50 MW Power Plant using FINPLAN and provide insights into the economic sustainability and profitability of the solar plant investment in Zambia.

2. Methodology

2.1 The Bangweulu Solar Power Plant

This study will analyse the development of a 50 MW Solar Power Plant. The construction phase is projected to span three years, from 2016 to 2018, followed by the commencement

of operations from 2019. The anticipated operational lifespan of the plant is 25 years. Table 1 provides details regarding the power plant and its financing arrangements.

Table 1. Bangweulu Solar Power Plant Characteristics and Financing Arrangements

Capacity	50 MW Solar Plant
Construction Period	3 Years (2016 to 2018)
Year of first operation	2019
Lifespan	25 Years
Revenue Projections	Electricity sales at ZMW 1.5 Annual production: 140 GWh
Investment	USD 37 million
Financial Assumptions	Inflation was steady at 9% Discount rate at 6%
Financing Structure	Equity: ZMW 623.5 million Loan: USD 13.2 Million
Financing currency	Foreign (USD) Local (ZMW)
Operation and Maintenance	USD 1.5 Million Annually
Taxes	VAT at 16% on 80% of the investment

2.2 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The financial analysis will utilize FINPLAN, a financial analysis tool for strategic planning and decision-making. Data will be analysed for the construction and operation phases of the solar power plant. Key data includes initial investment costs, operational expenses, revenue projections from energy sales, tax implications, and financial details related to loans and equity. A model will be constructed to forecast the solar power plant's cash flows throughout its anticipated lifespan, considering factors like electricity generation capacity, expected energy output, maintenance expenses, inflation rates, and energy price projections. FINPLAN will compute the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) to assess profitability. A higher IRR and positive NPV indicate greater project profitability. FINPLAN will further analyze financial ratios like leverage, Breakeven Point, Debt Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR), and Debt to Equity Ratio to evaluate the project's financial robustness and risk exposure.

2.3 Scenarios or sensitivity analysis

This financial analysis aims to assess the sensitivity of key financial indicators, specifically the Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which signify the profitability of dividends disbursed to shareholders. It investigates variations in three

pivotal parameters: (1) reduction in electricity prices; (2) increased production; and (3) adjustments to the loan payback period which plays a critical role in determining the financial feasibility of the project:

- Scenario One: Analysing the impact of price reduction on dividends (Sensitivity: 25%, 50%, 75% price reduction).
- Scenario Two: Evaluating the effect of production changes on dividends (Sensitivity: 25%, 50%, 75%, 100% increase in production).
- Scenario Three: Assessing the effect of varying loan repayment periods (Sensitivity: 5 years, 10 years, 15 years and 20 years repayment periods).

3. Results

3.1 Scenario One. Effect of change in Electricity Price on dividends

In this scenario, we varied the electricity prices by reducing it to 25%, 50% and 75% below the base price of ZMW 1.5 per KWh (Figure 2). The base price (ZMW 1.5) had the highest dividends and also had the lowest waiting period for shareholders to access their dividends (3 years). The mean annual increase in shareholder dividend was ZMW 27.8m using the base price scenario ($y = 27.812x - 121.87$; $R^2 = 0.9582$). On the other hand, at sensitivity level of 25% price reduction, the dividends increased at a mean annual rate of ZMW 24.4 M which is a 3.4 M reduction in shareholding dividends from the base price. However, there is a 4-year lag time before dividends are accessed. At 50% price reduction (ZMW 1.125) the shareholder dividends get reduced by nearly half of the base price to a mean annual dividend increase of ZMW 13.8m. There is also a 12-year lag time before dividends get accessed.

Figure 2. Shareholder dividends at reduced electricity prices of 25%, 50% and 75% below the base price of ZMW 1.5

The 75% price reduction also represents the current price for electricity in Zambia (ZMW 0.375). At this price the Solar Power Plant, this is not profitable (NPV -2813.58; IRR 0%) and there is no incentive for setting it up. Figure 3 shows that profitability can be achieved at 25% and 50% price reduction, but not at 75%.

Figure 3. Profitability of the Bangweulu Solar Power Plant at varying levels of price sensitivity

3.2 Scenario Two. Impact of change in quantity of electricity produced on dividends

Under this scenario we varied the quantity of electricity produced by the power plant. We made an assumption that the plant is producing at less than 100%, hence it's possible to increase production by 25%, 50% and 75%.

Figure 4. Change in shareholder dividends with increasing production levels

The results show that increasing base productivity by 25%, 50%, and 75% increased shareholding dividends at a mean annual rate of ZMW 42.14 (25%), ZMW 50.97 (50%) and 59.79 (75%) from ZMW 33.3 million (base level). Unlike change in pricing, change in production did not result in lag time before dividends could be paid and shareholders did not have to wait to get their dividends. As indicated in Figure 5, all the sensitivity scenarios for increasing productivity were profitable with positive NPVs and high IRR. Increasing production exponentially increased profitability assuming all generated power was sold.

Figure 5. Change in profitability at base, 25%, 50% and 75% production sensitivity scenarios

3.3 Scenario 3. Effect of varying loan repayment period on dividends

In this scenario, we varied the period of loan repayment for the financing loan. The sensitivity was set at 5 years, 10 years, 15 years and 20 years. The results show that in the long term the dividends do not change significantly with the change in loan repayment periods. The overall long-term mean annual dividend change in the different repayment periods is about ZMW 32.9 million (5 Years), ZMW 33.2 million (10 Years), ZMW 33.3 million (15 Years) and ZMW 33.4 million (20 Years) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Change in shareholder dividends in the long-term loan repayment period

In the short term, shorter periods of loan repayment are more profitable. Figure 7 indicates that the 5-year loan repayment in the short term generated a mean annual shareholder dividend of ZMW 24.9 million compared to the ZMW 20.86 for the 20-year loan repayment period.

Figure 7. Shareholder dividends in the short-term period of loan repayment

Generally, plant profitability reduced with increased loan repayment period. Both the NPV and the IRR were higher in the short repayment period (5 years) compared to the subsequent longer repayment periods (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Change in plant profitability (NPV, IRR) at various loan repayment periods

5. Discussion

The findings of this study shed light on the complex interplay between pricing strategies, productivity enhancements, and loan repayment periods in the context of a Solar Power Plant in Zambia. The analysis reveals that while price reductions of up to 50% below the base price remain profitable for the plant, reducing prices to the level of current hydro-electricity prices for Zambia (ZMW 0.375 per kWh) would result in unprofitability. This underscores the delicate balance that must be struck between affordability for consumers and ensuring the financial viability of the plant.

Moreover, the study highlights the significant impact of productivity improvements on shareholding dividends. Increasing base productivity by 25%, 50%, and 75% led to corresponding increases in dividends, showcasing the potential for enhanced operational efficiency to drive financial performance. Unlike changes in pricing, productivity enhancements did not result in a lag time before dividends could be paid, indicating the immediate benefits of investing in improving productivity.

Furthermore, the analysis of different loan repayment periods revealed that while there were marginal changes in annual dividends for long-term loans, the overall impact on shareholder returns remained relatively stable. On the other hand, short term loan repayment exhibited higher shareholder profitability compared to long-term repayments. However, the study emphasizes the importance of financial planning and coordination with lenders when considering extended loan repayment periods, as these may have implications for the financial performance and sustainability of the Solar Power Plant.

Government policy should focus on reducing solar power prices by up to 50% below the base price (ZMW 1.5) to make it more affordable for consumers while ensuring profitability for the Solar Power Plant, with the aim of increasing access to clean energy and promoting solar power adoption in Zambia. On the other hand, Government focus on increasing base productivity to above 75% to enhance the efficiency and output of the Solar Power Plant,

which may involve investments in technology, training, and infrastructure. Further, policy should be focussed on loans with short term repayment periods in order to increase on profitability and sustainability.

7. Conclusion and recommendation

7.1 Conclusion

The study provides insights into the financial performance and sustainability of a Solar Power Plant in Zambia, focusing on pricing strategies, productivity enhancements, and loan repayment periods. The findings suggest that significant price reductions can maintain profitability, emphasizing the need for a balance between affordability and financial viability. Increasing productivity levels correlates with higher dividends, highlighting the importance of efficiency and output improvement. Additionally, government focussing on short term loan repayment periods is crucial for the plant's financial health and sustainability. Government policy should encourage price reductions to optimum levels, enhanced productivity even at the expense of price increase and using short term loans which generate higher dividends in the short term but with comparable shareholding value in the long term.

7.2 Recommendations

- Implement price reductions for solar power of up to 50% to increase affordability and uptake.
- Boost productivity levels beyond 75% for Bangweulu Solar plan to increase profitability.
- Carefully consider the impact of extended loan repayment periods on financial performance and sustainability. Preference can be on loans with shorter repayment periods

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